

The Labor Market and Output in Bangladesh: Does Okun's Law Stand Still?

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Abstract

Unemployment, an important macroeconomic problem plays a crucial role in developing economies. High unemployment gives signal that labor resources are not being used efficiently. Hence, targeting full employment should be a major macroeconomic aim of any government. In macroeconomic literature there is a well known premise called Okun's Law, which states the negative relationship between unemployment rate and real GDP (or economic growth). The core purpose of this paper is to evaluate the relationship between unemployment and real GDP considering Bangladesh as a case study. The sample covers annual data from 1972/73 to 2011/12. This paper examines whether there exists an Okun type relationship between this two macro variable in BD economy. The empirical results show that the negative relationship between output and unemployment is present. And there is no long run relationship between economic growth and unemployment.

Keywords: Okun's Law, output gap, cointegration, Granger causality,

1 Introduction

In macroeconomic framework, Okun's Law is a well known relationship, which states that there is a negative relationship between unemployment rate and real GDP. When growth of economy remains below its potential rate or turns depressing unemployment rate will increase as firms fail to generate sufficient revenues to fund their excess workforce. The relationship between this two variable is explained and summarized by famous Okun's Law. Okun's Law continues to be cited as part of a set of core beliefs in macroeconomics. As a rule of thumb, Okun's Law provides policymakers with a rough guide to the employment effect on output growth. The empirical estimates of Okun's coefficient, which is a measure of the responsiveness of unemployment to output growth, are crucial as they indicate the cost of unemployment in terms of economic growth or output. In the sixties and seventies the trade-off between GDP growth and unemployment was clear and undeniable. "Okun's Law" was regarded as one of the most trustworthy macroeconomic relations at that time.

The purpose of this paper attempts to answer the following main question: Does there exist an Okun-type relationship between output and unemployment in BD economy? If yes, then how does it look like?

The methodological approach and the estimation results discussed in the article are presented as follows. After the introduction, section 2 briefly reviews the existing literature on Okun's Law. Section 3 describes the data while section 4 is devoted to Okun's Law modeling strategy. Section 5 shows the estimation results showing unit root and Granger-Causality test and section 6 then concludes.

2. Literature Review and Empirical Evidence of Okun's Law

Okun's (1962) original work states that a one percent point reduction in unemployment rate would increase output by approximately 3 percent. Okun found that the relationship was about 3 to 1. Therefore to avoid the waste of unemployment, the economy must continually expand.

Prachowny (1993) found that changes in output will result in changes in efficiency of production. Other important determinants of output include the amount of time worked and exploitation of facility space. For him, Okun's law gives only a partial measure of the relationship between unemployment and GDP.

Christian E. Weber (1996) investigated Okun's law and stated that it is traditionally associated measure of output gap to the unemployment rate which has been one of the facts of the business cycle. Dany Lang et.al (2009) enlightened the connection between fluctuations in unemployment and growth, the most primary lag growth shock impacts the current unemployment rate.

Freeman (2001) uses new developments in trend/cycle decomposition to test Okun's Law for a panel of ten industrial countries. He found that Okun's original estimate for the U.S. of three points of real GDP growth for each one percent reduction in the unemployment rate now averages at just under two points of real GDP growth for the sample countries. Pooled estimates for Europe are smaller than estimates for the rest of the sample. Further, this article finds that omission of capital and labor inputs may have biased previous estimates. Freeman concluded that the law is still capable of providing estimates of the effects of unemployment on GDP. Dornbusch *et.al* (2001) also supported Okun's view. They argue that forgone output is the major cost of unemployment, and if the loss is very high it could lead to recession.

Leopold Soegner and Alfred Stiassny (2002) tested Okun's law and claim a negative association between the unemployment rate and the real output (GDP).

Roger Perman and Christophe Tavera (2005) observed the Okun's Law coefficient forms a main macroeconomic measure under the deviations of unemployment to the fluctuations in economic activity.

Perman and Tavera (2007) tested for the presence of convergence of the Okun's Law coefficient (OLC) among several alternative groups of European economies. They used a testing procedure suggested by Evans in order to investigate the convergence or non – convergence of the OLC in several groups of European countries by examining how the cross –country variance of the OLC evolves over time in these groups. A hypothesis of medium – term convergence of the OLC is rejected for most of the European country groups examined.

Ho-Chuan Huang and Shu-Chin Lin (2008), motivated by a simple theoretical model, proposed the Bayesian approach for estimating Okun's coefficients using U.S. quarterly data from 1948: Q1 to 2006: Q1. The results showed that there

is overwhelming evidence in favor of smooth –time – varying Okun's law which is positively related to productivity trend. Also their results indicated that the commonly – used Okun's law coefficient can lead to inappropriate results.

Turturean (2008) based on the inflation rate and unemployment rate registered in Romania for the period 1993 – 2004, examined how to show Okun's Law. Results consisted of two distinct models explaining the dependency between the GDP's growth rate and unemployment rate's growth and vice

versa. This shows that in the case of Romania there was no two – way relationship using the same model, the direct and mutual dependencies between growth of unemployment rate and the growth rate of GDP's as shown in the original formulation of Okun's Law.

Christian Pierdzioch et.al (2009) found a significant negative relationship between the anticipated change in unemployment rate and the projected growth rate of real output.

Several studies have highlighted the limitations of Okun's law. Such study includes those by Altig, *et al* (1997), Blinder (1997) and Lee (2000). These studies concluded that Okun's framework does not take into consideration factors that are also important in influencing changes in output and unemployment, such as labour force participation, productivity and production functions.

3 Data Sources, Measurement and Description

The data set is annual, spanning 1972/73 through 2011/12. Data of unemployment (U_t) and output, Gross Domestic Product Y_t data is in real terms. Series data on unemployment is almost unavailable for which we had to regress that manually. For potential output Y_t^* , Y_t is regressed on trend variable and consider fitted value as potential output. In equation (1) output gap variable is the difference between real GDP and potential GDP and unemployment gap

$(U_t - U_t^*)$ is the difference between the observed and natural rate of unemployment.

This paper examines the relationship between unemployment and economic growth using time series data. To test if the series are non-stationary or contain a unit root, we focus on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) test. If the test indicates non-stationarity for any series, we conclude that the series has a unit root. We find that all the series have a unit root. We have used EViews 7 as statistical software package.

4 Theoretical Framework

Macroeconomic theory provides us with relatively few models linking the unemployment rate to GDP growth. It was Okun (1962) who focused the discussion on the empirical relationship between unemployment and GDP variations. The explanation of Okun's law is very simple; due to changes in aggregate demand, firms alter their output plans and this leads to changes in labour demand and therefore affects the unemployment rates.

Okun's law was consistent with the relationship between unemployment rate and real production for many decades.

Even if the negative relationship between the “gap” of unemployment rate and the increase of real production has been quite stable, the absolute value of Okun's coefficient seems to vary in different time periods and from country to country (Altig et. Al, 2002).

As suggested by Okun (1970), there are two classes of Okun's law specifications: first is the ‘First difference model’ and second is the ‘Gap model’. In Okun's original paper, the estimation is done using the gap method, as in Equation (1), where unemployment is related to deviations of output from potential GDP.

$$Y_t - Y_t^* = \alpha + \beta (U_t - U_t^*) + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

And $\beta < 0$

Where Y_t^* refers the log of potential output, U_t is the log of observed unemployment, U_t^* is the natural rate of unemployment or the corresponding potential value. where α is the intercept, β is Okun's coefficient computing that how much variation in the unemployment rate to changes in output, and ε_t is the disturbance term. Equation (1) can be re estimated as (see Mitchell and Muysken, 2002),

$$U_t = \alpha + \beta Y_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

And $\beta < 0$

The Gap model has been chosen for further analysis of the okun's law, where the left-hand side represents the output gap ($Y_t - Y_t^*$) and right-hand side represents the unemployment gap ($U_t - U_t^*$).

Thus, the difference between the observed and potential real GDP postulates the fluctuations in output. Similarly, the difference between the observed and natural rate of unemployment refers the cyclical rate of unemployment. β is the Okun coefficient, which measures the responsiveness between the cyclical unemployment and the output gap. Since the relationship between output gap and cyclical unemployment is inversely related, the sign of β is negative.

The second alternative is to use Okun's first-difference method, as shown in (3) which will test the relative sensitivity of output to unemployment changes. According to the first-difference model, the link between the natural log of real output ($Y_t - Y_{t-1}$) and the natural log of unemployment rate ($U_t - U_{t-1}$) is given as:

$$Y_t - Y_{t-1} = a - b(U_t - U_{t-1}) + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Estimation of b will give the Okun coefficient. Equation (3) states that there is a negative relationship between output growth and unemployment rate, but it does not give the causal relationship between the two. Thus we will have to carry out a Granger causality test to determine this.

This study uses data on the unemployment rate and real GDP in order to estimate Okun's coefficient. The data derives from Economic Review published by the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics. All series are annual, covering data of thirty seven years. In his first research, Okun used data from Gross National Product. Later, many academics have estimated Okun's coefficient using Gross Domestic Product (Harris and Silverstone 2001) and production as well (Prachowny 1993, and Freeman 2000).

5. Estimation

5.1 Econometrics Methodology

5.1.1 Estimations of Okun Coefficient and their Applications

The purpose of this paper is to estimate the Okun coefficient. Since the value of the NAIRU is not determined, the OLS estimations of [2] and [3] are preceded based on the following two approaches of estimating the NAIRU.

Approach A – NAIRU is approximated by its historical average

The data range is in the period from 1973 to 2012 and the historical average of the annual unemployment is used to approximate the NAIRU.

Approach B – NAIRU is approximated by the one period lag of unemployment rate (Time-varying NAIRU)

The OLS estimation of the Okun coefficient through this approach is represented by (1) and the NAIRU is time-varying throughout the period.

5.1.2 Baseline Results

So finally our baseline Okun's Law equations for Bangladesh are as follows which are just the equation [2] and [3] respectively.

$$\Delta U_t = \alpha + \beta \Delta Y_t + \varepsilon_t \dots \quad (4)$$

and $\beta < 0$

$$\Delta(Y_t - Y_{t-1}) = a - b(U_t - U_{t-1}) + \varepsilon_t \quad (5)$$

The equations were estimated as an OLS regression. The estimated coefficients of the baseline equation are reported in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Regression Result

variables	Dependent variable	Constant	$\beta \Delta Y_t$	$\delta \Delta(U_t - U_{t-1})$	R-Sq	R-Sq(adj)
EQ[4]	ΔU_t	0.0428 (0.86)	-0.000001 (-0.01)	-	0.0%	0.0%
EQ[5]	$\Delta(Y_t - Y_{t-1})$	-3 (-0.02)	-	-1496 (9.89)	73.1%	72.4%

Notes: Dependent variable is inflation ($\Delta^2 \pi_t$). t-Statistics are displayed in brackets.

* denotes rejection of H_0 at 1%, 5% and 10% level: the coefficient is zero

** denotes rejection of H_1 at 1%, 5% and 10% level: the coefficient is not equal to zero

Source: Authors' own calculation.

All the estimated coefficients have expected sign. While the size of the coefficient of equation [5] is surprisingly large, the R-Sq and adjusted R-Sq show expected values. But the case is opposite in equation [4]. The size of the coefficient is logical but the R-Sq and adjusted R-Sq show unexpected values. A one percentage increase of economic growth will reduce the unemployment by 0.000001 percentages. Although a weak statistical result is obtained, it may still be valuable to treat the set of estimated parameters as a rough reference of predicting the real output growth when unemployment rate is affected by policy changes.

5.3 Unit Root Test

Most macroeconomic time-series are non-stationary, i.e. having unit roots. The variables tend to show similar increasing or decreasing patterns over time. Hence, before proceeding with further analysis, the data must be tested for the existence of time series problems using the stationary stochastic process. A test of stationarity (or non stationarity) that is widely used is the unit root test. Unit root test is important in examining the stationarity of a time series, because a non-stationary regressor invalidates many standard empirical results. The existence of stochastic trend is determined by testing the presence of unit roots in time series data. So this analysis begins by pre-testing both standard Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test. The null hypothesis of these tests is that series are non-stationary.

The ADF tests assume that the error terms are statistically independent and have a constant variance. This assumption may not be true of all the data used, and so the Phillip-Perron test is used to relax the above assumptions and permit the error disturbances to be heterogeneously distributed. The results proved that both variables are non-stationary and so the regression test was applied to the first difference.

Table 2: unit root test (non stationarity)

variable	ADF(LEVEL)		PP (LEVEL)	
	InTERCEpt	TREND & InTERCEPT	InTERCEPT	TREND & InTERCEPT
rgdp	2.5372 (L=2)	0.9952	3.9780*	1.5273
unem	-0.3985	1.9916	-0.5263	2.0353

Table 3: unit root test (stationarity)

variable	ADF (1st difference)		PP (1st difference)	
	InTERCEpt	TREND & InTERCEPT	InTERCEPT	TREND & InTERCEPT
rgdp	-4.6621	-5.5070	-4.6552	-5.5059
unem	-5.8982	5.9603	-5.9170	-5.9682

So our conclusion is as follows:

Table 4:

Variable	Order Of Integration
RGDP	I(1)
UNEM	I(1)

Where

RGDP= Real GDP

UNEM= Unemployment Rate

5.1.4 Co-integration Test:

Checking Long Run Relationship

If the unit root results point out that the variables are integrated at same order, the next step is to calculate the long run relationship in the form as: where left hand side is the output gap and right hand side is unemployment gap, and μ is the white noise disturbance term. If the sequence of residuals from this regression is stationary, the sequences OG and UG are said to be co-integrated of order (1, 1). On the other hand, if these residuals are non-stationary, it is concluded that there is no long run equilibrium relationship or no cointegration lies between the output gap and the unemployment gap.

Since the regression models include two variables, we use the Engle-Granger test for checking the long run relationship. The result is showed below:

Table 5: unit root test of the residuals (ϵ)

variable	ADF (LEVEL)		PP (LEVEL)	
	InTERCEpt	TREND & InTERCEPT	InTERCEPT	TREND & InTERCEPT
ϵ_t	-0.1041	1.0797	-0.6164	1.6017

From the unit root test result of the disturbance term we see that it is nonstationary at level which postulates that the variables are not cointegrated i.e. there is no long run or equilibrium relationship between economic growth and unemployment. So we cannot go for ECM.

5.5 Test for Granger Causality

A Series of Bivariate Presentation of the Variables

Since the integrated order of the variables is not same, we cannot go for the cointegration test rather the Granger Causality test. **Granger causality** is a technique for determining whether one [time series](#) is useful in forecasting another. GC tests can be placed in one of four categories: No causality, X causes Y only, Y causes X only, and a bi-directional causality, i.e., X causes Y and Y causes X simultaneously. The results of Granger causality are reported in Table-4.

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests			
Sample: 1973 -2010			
Lags: 1			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Decision
UNEMRT does not Granger Cause REALGDP	37	1.14879	Accept H_0
REALGDP does not Granger Cause UNEMRT		0.00026	Accept H_0
Lags: 2			
REALGDP does not Granger Cause UNEMRT	36	0.49405	Accept H_0
UNEMRT does not Granger Cause REALGDP		1.00979	Accept H_0
Lags: 3			
UNEMRT does not Granger Cause REALGDP	35	0.53187	Accept H_0
REALGDP does not Granger Cause UNEMRT		1.63562	Accept H_0
Lags: 4			
UNEMRT does not Granger Cause REALGDP	34	0.42791	Accept H_0
REALGDP does not Granger Cause UNEMRT		1.46477	Accept H_0
Lags: 5			
UNEMRT does not Granger Cause REALGDP	33	0.36156	Accept H_0
REALGDP does not Granger Cause UNEMRT		0.97936	Accept H_0
Lags: 6			
UNEMRT does not Granger Cause REALGDP	32	0.33049	Accept H_0
REALGDP does not Granger Cause UNEMRT		0.99410	Accept H_0
Lags: 7			
UNEMRT does not Granger Cause REALGDP	31	0.30177	Accept H_0
REALGDP does not Granger Cause UNEMRT		0.80985	Accept H_0
Lags: 8			
UNEMRT does not Granger Cause REALGDP	30	0.20592	Accept H_0
REALGDP does not Granger Cause UNEMRT		1.46544	Accept H_0
Lags: 9			
UNEMRT does not Granger Cause REALGDP	29	0.18679	Accept H_0
REALGDP does not Granger Cause UNEMRT		1.26937	Accept H_0

Clearly we see that in all cases there is no causality between the variables. Unemployment does not granger cause Real GDP or economic growth and Real GDP does not granger cause Unemployment. The number of lags is based on the lowest value of Akaike Information criterion (AIC).

6. Conclusion

On this study we have estimated Okun's coefficients for Bangladesh using real GDP and unemployment rate. In conclusion we can say Okun's Law is able to explain the Bangladesh condition not very strongly. Any attempts to reduce unemployment will result in increasing the growth rate of the GDP not significantly. The prejudice that Okun's Law lost its instructive supremacy and that unemployment cannot be tackled by growth only. Policies that promote economic growth only are not

effective to bring back equilibrium in the labor market after a depressing shock. In order to resolve such crisis it is therefore necessary to combine Keynesian policies with those aimed at reducing the adjustment costs in the labor market. Obviously, the structure of the economy examined in this study differs from those of the U.S., Japan or Europe where Okun's law seems to work rather well as an empirical regularity.

However, the whole result should be treated with some skepticism because there is a lack of good time series data on unemployment (for which estimating NAIRU becomes hard), there is no scope for a formulation of the regression that allows for a perfect estimation of Okun's coefficient to show.

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Appendices

1. Appendix to Section 3: Data

variable	Description	Source	Available from
Y_t	Annual GDP series (at constant prices)	BBS, Statistical Year Book and Economic Review	1972/73 to 2012
$Y_t - Y_t^*$	Output gap (est)	Constructed	-
U_t	Unemployment rate (est)	BBS, Statistical Year Book and ILO and some constructed	Indefinite
$U_t - U_{t-1}$	Unemployment Gap	Constructed	-

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	REALGDP	UNEMRT
Mean	135290.4	2.804227
Median	52531.50	2.500000
Maximum	690500.0	4.300000
Minimum	3783.000	1.100000
Std. Dev.	156983.4	0.968151
Skewness	1.991320	0.167858
Kurtosis	7.011317	1.804321
Jarque-Bera	50.59081	2.442059
Probability	0.000000	0.294926
Sum	5141036.	106.5606
Sum Sq. Dev.	9.12E+11	34.68072
Observations	40	40

2. Tables and Illustrations

Filter presentation of real output or economic growth:

Figure 1:

Actual Output and Fitted Trend:

Figure 2:

Actual Unemployment Rate and Fitted Trend:

Figure 3

Figure 4

Seasonal Analysis for
Real GDP

Figure 5:

Seasonal Analysis for
Unemployment

